

CONCEPTUAL PROBLEMS OF SIMULTANEOUS TRANSLATION

Orunbaeva Uminiso Sharabidinovna

Ferghana State University,

Department of foreign languages and literature, teacher

Okhunov Asilbek Olimjon ugli

Ferghana Polytechnic Institute,

Department of "Teaching foreign languages and Uzbek language"

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Abstract. *Simultaneous translation in translation practice is one of the most diverse directions. This thesis is dedicated to the analysis of problems and some technologies that can be used in practice.*

Keywords: simultaneous translation, compression, strategy, text, memory, source language, speech speed, target language, spoken language, semantic segment

КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ СИНХРОННОГО ПЕРЕВОДА

Аннотация. *Синхронный перевод в переводческой практике является одним из самых разнообразных направлений. Данная дипломная работа посвящена анализу проблем и некоторых технологий, которые можно использовать на практике.*

Ключевые слова: синхронный перевод, компрессия, стратегия, текст, память, исходный язык, скорость речи, целевой язык, разговорный язык, смысловой сегмент.

INTRODUCTION

So far, Western scientists have worked on the methods and techniques of the synchronous translation and methods of other foreign languages. Not all the methods they used can be used in English Simultaneous Translation. Because unlike European languages, the Uzbek language belongs to another language of other languages and its syntactic and morphological construction is radically different. Therefore, through this issue, we have targeted a deep research work on this issue, claiming that Uzbek-English and English-Uzbek synchronous methods and theories were not conducted. Not only the synchronous translation process, but also the preparation of translators are a very complex practical process. In order to successfully pass through this practice, translators use a variety of methods and roads, more precisely, strategies. The strategies for the perfect acquisition strategies are in the cause of the problem are ways to introduce certain methods in practice.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Strategies in the synchronous translation are divided into 2 large groups: A) strategies that increase understanding of speech in a synchronous translation; b) strategies that help express opinion in translation. These strategies are divided into several more types:

A. Strategies to increase speech in synchronous translation:

1. Preparation for the process;
2. Invention in advance;
3. Separation of pieces;

B. Strategies that help you express opinion:

1. Text coordination strategies in the original language:
 - a) syntactic transformation; b) literal translation;
2. Text coordination strategies in translation:

a) shortening or extension of the text; b) stylistic strategies; c) demonstration;

3. Required strategies:

a) selection; Deleting; b) generalization; c) simplification;

4. Correction strategies:

a) self-correcting; b) decide not to correct anything;

5. General Strategy:

a) observation or control.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

If we paralyze the classified strategies one by one, we will have interesting information. The preparation strategies for incoming speech in the synchronous translation cover or translates as expected texts, the terminology of the terminology of the conference participants. Invention strategy is characterized by dividing the text to the translator in advance, and that it is characterized by dividing the analysis of ideas (segments).

The second type of strategy itself itself is 5 types. The first type of type (qualifying strategies in the "textual language) will include syntactic transformation and literal. The syntactic transformation is a method of changing the location of sync translation elements. The literal translation is its opposite, from which numbers are used to provide a list of names.

Reducing text, which is one of the text coordination strategies in translation means the removal of excess data by the translator. The extension of the text is the grantation of additional information in translation when the need is needed. The stylistic strategy means to find the best methods of expressing opinions, and showing the methods of displaying the methods of these expression means through super profitable elements (intonation, pause and b.)

Necessary strategies use when they feel that translators are not acting. These problems may vary: the data overflows, fatigue, interference, and many other reasons. In similar situations, which information or leaving is selected. Under the time pressure, the translator will deletely deletes excess data from memory, a generalized information in the original language or simplifies texts that are difficult.

Under the correctional strategy, combined strategy, combined by the interpreter, the correctness of the terms that are neglected in the speech. Sometimes translators decide not to correct them if they feel the impact of the audience to avoid inconvenience.

The overall strategy covers the observation (control) strategy. In this case, the translator examines meaning between the news coming with already translated ideas in order to control the productivity of activity.

Circle of Kalina is not included in the classification of synchronous transmission strategies, the time push strategy is described in Gayyl and Donate's scientific work. This strategy is characterized by translators as they cannot translate a sentence, the closing of time when they fail to translate a sentence.

In order to find out which of the above-mentioned strategies in English-Uzbek languages, we reviewed the synchronous translation process used in one scientific-practical conference. We attended 2 translators in the process of 20 minutes of sync translation, which we chose as a learning object for our research. The average speed of the English language message was 110-120 words / minutes (110 to 50-20 words), but the average speed of delivery in translation was 80 words / minutes. The difference was due to the different language systems:

- in the event of an English language, the appearance of the verbs,

- the use of ravines before the verbs, the presence of actions in English,
- prelogs of grammatical meanings,
- expressed by utility words.

The "Text Reduction strategy is not a selected strategy based on the Uzbek and English-speaking characteristics, but a reduction in the nature of the synchronous translation process. Because in syncora translation, translators are only trying to deliver the main meaning, unlike written translation. They do not have anything to do with the meaning of unnecessary data in translation. At the same time, it is divided through time, and the text of the translation is short, but significantly meaningful ideas are in place. Based on the tempo of the speech of the speaker's speech in the Synchronian Translation, the number of interpreter's speech is given in the following table:

Speaking speech rate, number of joints / min	Translator Speech rate, the number of joints / min	Reduction amount (compared to written translation), %
166-180	206	30,3
181-195	211	
196-210	215	
211-225	217	
226-240	222	
256 and more	226	

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it was noted that in the process of synchronous translation in the English-Uzbek languages, 7 different strategies were used at different levels. These strategies are based on only "syntax transformation", "Syntax transformation", "Single parts" and "pre-examination" and "pre-examination" are based on the characteristics of English and Uzbek languages. Others are general strategies that are subject to oral translation that arise in the practice of synchronous translation.

The above points were covered with a certain environment of the synchronous translation during the exploration conquests in the explanations in the explanations that were not formed on the perfect or sowed results.

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